
VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF DEVELOPED MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT TEST FOR SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS TWO IN BAYELSA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the validity and reliability of mathematics achievement test for senior secondary schools in Bayelsa state. Two (2) research questions directed the study. The study embraced Instrumentation plan. Instrumentation research design was used for the study because the study aimed at new content and procedures for education activities. The study's sample consists of 1026 test takers from both public and private schools. The study's sample was compiled using stratified sampling techniques and simple random sampling techniques which was based on school location. The research instrument was designed by the researcher. The 100 items in the instrument were selected from the Bayelsa State Ministry of Education curriculum in line with WAEC guideline which was guided with table of specification. The test instrument was analyzed using Principle Component Analysis (PCA) and Cronbach's alpha KR-20 reliability estimate. The study found out among others that the mathematics achievement test (MAT) for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State has both content and construct validity, the MAT for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State has a reliability of 0.99. In line with the findings and conclusions of the study, it was recommended among others that Test item makers in Nigeria should compel the Federal Ministry of Education to ensure examination bodies to use only psychometrically valid and reliable test to assess students' achievement during external certificate examination to reduce mass failure among students.

Keyword: Validity, Reliability, Mathematics achievement test

Introduction

The success of any educational institution aiming for goal achievement depends on its foundation. For a nation to attain sustainable development in all areas of life, the foundation of the educational sector must be effectively planned. This is why the United Nations (UN) in collaboration with UNESCO formulated global goals and policies that will enhance the living condition of its citizens in the world. Among these global goals are Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). As noted by Nwabeze (2021) critics of the MDGs complained of a lack of analysis and justification towards the chosen objects, constraint measures of some goals and unequal progress among others. However, the goals are comprehensive and interdependent. One of the goals in sustainable development is the Goal four. Odili (2019) noted that the goal four largely covered the education sector and it states as follows: "Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote life-long learning opportunities for all". Burchi and Rippin (2015) opined that the goal four (4) is intended for an inclusive and equitable quality education and promotes life-long learning opportunities for all. This set goal can only be achieved when meaningful education stakeholders develop valid and reliable test that measure and tap the constructs of the goal four targets through teaching and learning in the classroom situation. Ruggiero (2020) supported the above key points by stating that students are involved in critical thinking, describing critical thinking as a mental readiness that formulate and proffer solution to a problem, making decision, or fulfill a desire to understand.

As a result of the importance of education to the realization of goals, every creative government, both local and states have placed a premium on the education of its citizens by developing an instrument that is covered in higher level of cognitive domain that will enhance their critical thinking skill and problem solving ability. The amount of education received is determined when students are assessed with valid and reliable instrument. It should be noted that assessment of students' learning experience is crucial in teaching and learning process. One of the outstanding and exceptional assessment measures and procedures widely employed and used is the achievement test.

Achievement tests are interval in nature meaning that in educational measurement, there is no zero with regard to achievement tests. Achievement tests are of two broad categories which are the classroom test (popularly called teacher-made test) and standardized tests (Igabari & Okagbare, 2023). Teacher-made- tests are those tests constructed and given by individual teachers in determining and evaluating their own classroom instructions while standardized tests are those tests constructed and given under the supervision of examination authorities outside the classroom. Standardized tests possess better psychometric qualities or properties than teacher-made tests (Osadebe, 2014). Opong as cited in Nwabeze (2021) opined that majority of teacher developed tests do not meet the quality (validity and reliability) of a good test due to unskilled constructs of validation and standardization of achievement tests. Teachers hurriedly and poorly develop achievement test in disorderliness resulting to invalid and unreliable tests. Classroom teachers need to be more acquainted with the process and procedures of the design of a reliable test in assessing the ability of students in subject contents. Igabari and Okagbare (2023) noted that classroom teachers can only prepare tests of achievement under the supervision of experts or who have worked with experts in test development. According to Igabari and Okagbare (2023), it will enhance the determination of the quality of test such as item discrimination, item difficulty and item guessing parameters as much as the validity and reliability of the test. The teacher-developed test that meets the quality of a well designed test used in assessing the performance of students in mathematics will prepare them for external examination in mathematics.

The aim of a teacher-made test in secondary schools is to determine how effective teaching and how well students have learned the material, as well as to provide the teacher with needed information to improve teaching. Teacher-made tests can also help to motivate students by giving them rewards (high test scores, gold stars, and so on) and feedback (how to improve weaknesses, how to make the most of strengths). The teacher-made test is also important because it helps administrators, parents, and community leaders to know what's happening and how prepared students are for external examination. Kinyua and Okunya (2014) stated that teacher-made tests are expected to prepare students for better academic performance in standardized test usually conducted by various examination bodies such as WAEC, NECO, JAMB, and the NABTEB. In contexts where students take a standardized test such as national examinations for entry into tertiary learning institutions, the more effective the teacher made test becomes, the better and the performance on the standardized test is likely to be (Igabari & Okagbare, 2023). Unfortunately, studies and reviews on the impact of teacher-made tests on students' performance in the standardized test have not been very positive. Studies have shown that the academic performance of students in a standardized test conducted by examination bodies such as WAEC and the NECO, were discovered to be low (Igabari & Okagbare, 2023) despite the high-grade score by students in teachers made tests. Most secondary school students fail standardized test despite their possession of excellent grades or scores in teacher made tests (Igabari & Okagbare, 2023).

The development of valid and reliable tests in various subject areas especially mathematics has not been given good and adequate attention in the senior secondary schools in Nigeria. It has been observed that most teachers are not good in constructing tests in their various subject areas (Osadebe, 2012). It is expected that schools should have enough valid and reliable tests for assessing their students when they have covered the curriculum content to prepare them for external examination bodies such as WAEC and among others. Test validity is defined as a test which measures what it is designed to measure. The ability of an instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure is referred to as its validity. Simply put, validity is the extent to which the object test measures the content it claims to assess. Only judgments about the interpretation of a mathematics objective test are valid. Nworgu (2015) defined validity as the extent to which an instrument, such as a test, measured its intended objective. Content, criterion-related, contemporaneous, predictive, face, and construct validity are the several types of validity. All of these types of validity could be demonstrated by objective tests. The content validity of an objective test refers to how well it represents the whole mathematics curriculum. According to Diakeleho (2021), the content validity of a test examined the subject matter and behavioural objectives under consideration. The level to which the stem or question, tasks on the objective exam are indicative of the overall behavior the test was supposed to sample determines it. It should be highlighted that in terms of achievement test content validity, test makers focus on convergence and representativeness rather than test scores or statistical calculations. Achievement test should be generated to ensure validity of the instrument.

On the other hand, a reliable test is a test whose measures are consistent and stable. This means that when one uses a reliable test to measure a similar behaviour, the same outcomes are expected (Igabari & Okagbare, 2023). An unreliable test is a test which today gives one result and at other times gives a totally different result, such a test cannot produce acceptable results. Achievement tests are expected to be reliable. In other words, Mathematics Achievement Tests, whether teacher-made or standardized, are expected to measure the knowledge of the students in the content area at all times, and for any group of students. Hence, they are supposed to be stable and consistent. In other words there is a need

to develop a valid and reliable instrument that is covered in higher level of cognitive domain that will enhance their ability to think and solve societal problems.

Statement of the problem

According to WAEC Chief Examiner's Report (2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020), candidates that sat for WASSCE at these periods lack skills in answering almost all the questions asked in general objective mathematics test. Students' performances in various school subjects, most especially mathematics in teacher-constructed tests and in external examination over the years, have been very poor and not satisfactory. It is not positively known if the setback of low performance is due to the student's learning ability, or inability of mathematics teachers to develop a valid and reliable test for assessment of students. To the best of the researcher's knowledge no research has been carried out to find solution to the problem of poor performance of students in both teacher-made test and standardized tests in relation to the validity and reliability of developed mathematics achievement test for senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The problem of this study in question form is: How valid and reliable is the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT)?

Research Questions

The research questions below gave direction to the study

1. What is the validity of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) developed for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the reliability of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) developed for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State?

Purpose of the Study

1. Find out the validity of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) developed for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State.
2. Determine the reliability of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) in Bayelsa State.

Significance of the study

The outcome of this study may be useful to education stakeholders like examination bodies, government, policy makers' principals and teachers, curriculum planners, and research institutions. It attempts to fill the existing gap in research in the field of test development.

Research Design

Instrumentation was used for the study. Ileh (2017) defined instrumentation design as the procedure that is used by measurement experts for developing tests or modifying an existing instrument for collecting data.

Population of the study

The population of the study is 19693 which comprised 13705 public and 5988 private senior secondary school two (SSII) students in Bayelsa State (Akemiyefa et al., 2025)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study consists of 1026 students. Stratified sampling techniques and simple random sampling techniques were used to draw the sample for the study. At the first instance, 30% of the entire schools in public and government approved private senior secondary schools were selected using stratification method of sampling. The stratification was based school location. Using the stratification, twenty four (24) schools which constitute 30% of the entire schools in urban area were selected and forty (40) schools which constitute 30% of the entire schools in rural area were selected making a total of 64 public schools that were

selected while 30 private schools in rural and 77 private schools in urban making a total of 107 private schools. Therefore the total number of sampled schools in the study is 171 public and private schools in the eight local government areas of Bayelsa State. Secondly, 6 students were drawn from each sampled school through simple random sampling techniques (SRST) through balloting method.

Research Instrument

The research instrument was designed by the researcher. The items in the instrument were selected from the SS2 Bayelsa State Ministry of Education curriculum in line with WAEC guideline. 100 objectives test items were drawn based on table of specification that covered significant figures, decimal places, standard form and percentage error, fractions, ratios, simple and compound interest, profit and loss, indices, series and sequence, inequalities, algebraic process, quadratic equations, probabilities and statistics.

Method of Data Analysis

The research one question was answered using Principle Component Analysis (PCA) and research two was answered using Cronbach's alpha KR-20 reliability estimate.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Research Question One

What is the validity of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) developed for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State?

Table 1:

Validity of MAT using the Principle Component Analysis for STANDARDIZED RESIDUAL variance (in Eigenvalue units)

Table of STANDARDIZED RESIDUAL variance (in Eigenvalue units)

	EMPIRICAL		MODELED	
Total Raw variance in observations =	113.7	100%		100.0%
Raw variance explained by measures =	15.7	13.8%		14.0%
Raw variance explained by persons =	3.9	3.4%		3.5%
Raw variance explained by items =	11.8	10.4%		10.5%
Raw variance explained by variance (total) =	98.0	86.2%	100.0%	86.0%
Unexplained variance in 1 st contrast =	8.9	7.9%	9.12%	
Unexplained variance in 2 nd contrast =	5.4	4.7%	5.5%	
Unexplained variance in 3 rd contrast =	4.8	4.2%	4.9%	
Unexplained variance in 4 th contrast =	4.1	3.6%	4.2%	
Unexplained variance in 5 th contrast =	3.4	3.0%	3.5%	

The table 1 was interpreted by comparing the empirical values of the entries with the modeled value. It revealed that the total raw variance in observation agreed with the model value of 100%, raw variance explained by measures of 15.7% agreed with the model value of 14.0%, raw variance explained by persons of 3.4% agreed with the model value of 3.5%, and raw variance explained by items of 10.4% agreed with the model value of 10.5%. These values verify that the test has content and construct validity. The ratio of 7.9% of unexplained variance in 1st contrast to 10.4% of raw variance explained by items is 8.9. This seemed good since the 1st, 2nd and the 3rd were supposed to be more than 2.0 if they were indicating unidimensionality according to Aliyu 2018. This was further confirmed by a scree plot that is presented in figure 1.

STANDARDIZED RESIDUAL VARIANCE SCREE PLOT
 VARIANCE COMPONENT SCREE PLOT

The T is referred to the total raw variance in observation, M is raw variance explained by measure, U is the raw unexplained variance (total), I is raw variance explained by item on the plot graph, P is raw variance explained by person while 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, represented the unexplained variance in 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th contrast on the plot graph. Therefore, this confirmed that the data has both content and construct validity which indicate unidimensionality trait. Therefore it was found that the validity of the MAT for SS 2 students have both content and construct validity.

Research Question Two

What is the reliability of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) developed for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State?

To answer the research question, the 1026 measured person with that of 98 measured items were both considered here. The person [Cronbach’s alpha (KR-20)] reliability estimate of the 100 test was 0.85 see preliminary table2. This reliability was due to the spread of the persons’ ability in the analysis. Table 2 showed the raw score standard deviation of the sample 12.0 out of 100. When the item with negative point-measure correlation indices were deleted from the test, the reliability increased to 0.86 for 98 test items.

TABLE 2:
Reliability Table of 98 MAT ITEMS (Person-Units in wit)

	TOTAL SCORE	COUNT	MEASURE	MODEL ERROR	INFIT MNSQ	ZSTD	OUTFIT MNSQ	ZSTD
MEAN	605.3	1026.0	.00	.07	1.00	.0	1.00	.1
S.D.	138.5	.1	.68	.01	.06	2.8	.08	3.0
MAX	926.0	1026.0	2.33	.11	1.17	8.6	.23	9.3
MIN.	147.0	1026.0	-1.96	.06	.88	-5.0	.83	-5.1
REAL	RMSE	.07	TRUE SD	.67	SEPERATION	9.51	Item	RELIABILITY .99
MODEL	RMSE OF	.07	TRUE SD	.67	SEPERATION	9.63	Item	RELIABILITY .99
S. E	ITEM	MEAN	= .07					

MINIMUM EXTREME SCORE: 2 Item
 UMEAN=.0000 USCALE=1.0000

The table 10 showed the summary statistics of the 65 measured items. This investigated the representativeness of the items by checking the value given for item strata, item separation and item reliability. The item strata is 8.6, item separation is 9.63 while item reliability is 0.99. The reliability for the items was very good. That is, the chances that the difficulty ordering of the items be repeated if the test items were given to another group is extremely high. Thus, one can rely on the representativeness and reliability of the test items. Therefore, the reliability of the MAT items is 0.99

Discussion of Results

Validity of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State

Data obtained from research question one revealed that the mathematics achievement test (MAT) for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State has both content and construct validity which indicate unidimensionality trait. The result of the Principle Component Analysis of factor analysis was found to be of statistical significance and of practical importance since the standardized residual coefficient was not larger than 2.0 which showed unidimensionality (Green & Frantom, 2016). This was used to establish substantive and content aspect of the construct validity of the six facet Messick's principle. The evidence of the test validity shows a very good distribution of the mathematics test items. This was as result of the high degree of agreement among the judges on the percentage weights assigned to the educational objectives in the cognitive domain and content areas. The study is in line with study of Edjere (2022)

Reliability of the mathematics achievement test (MAT) for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State

Data obtained from research question two revealed that the mathematics achievement test (MAT) for SS 2 students in Bayelsa State has the reliability of 0.99. Internal consistency of the student ability measure was also high. When the items with negative point measure correlation is removed that helped the items to work together in the same way thereby enhancing the reliability of the test indicating that it was likely that the ordering of testees ability could be replicated because most of the variance in the measured scores was attributed to true variance of the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) construct. This was in support of the findings of Ahmad and Nordin (2017) with reliability that ranges between 0.97-0.99. The finding also supported Odo and Ugwoji (2016) whose developed test items went through the method of item analysis, difficulty index and discrimination index and used the kuder-Richardson formula 20 to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.88

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that the MAT is valid and reliable.

Recommendations

Based on the outcome of the study, it is therefore practically recommended that:

1. Researchers should use the test (MAT) as instrument for data gathering in their studies.
2. IRT and item parameter estimation software such as WINSTEP and other software should be made available in every tertiary institution in Bayelsa State for researchers to assess.
3. Test item makers in Nigeria should compel the Federal Ministry of Education to ensure examination bodies to use only psychometrically valid and reliable test to assess students' achievement during external certificate examination to reduce mass failure among students.

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